

Interferences : In the determination of Iron(III) at 0.4 M hydrochloric acid the effect of diverse ions were studied as described in earlier procedure. Chloride, bromide, ammonia, urea, thiourea, phthalate, nitrate, sulphate, alkali metals, alkaline earth metals and lanthanoid elements had no interfering effect upto 2000 ppm. The tolerance limits of other ions causing an error less than 2% are shown in parenthesis (in ppm) : phosphate (1200), fluoride (1400), arsenate (1600), UO_2^{2+} , Mn^{2+} (600), Fe^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cr^{3+} (800), Ni^{2+} (2000), Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} (1600), Zr^{4+} (400), W^{6+} (200), Mo^{6+} (15), V^{5+} (50), Al^{3+} (1200), Cu^{2+} (10), Ti^{4+} (50), La^{3+} (200).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr S. G. Tandon, Head, Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur for providing research facilities.

References

1. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, 1956, p. 524, 537, 544.
2. I. M. KOLTHOFF and E. B. SANDELL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", The MacMillan Co., New York, 1952, p. 636.
3. K. YAMAMOTO and K. OHASHI, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1977, 88, 141.
4. K. SATYANARAYANA and R. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 63.
5. L. G. SILLEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1956, 10, 185.

Morpholine-4-Carbodithioate as a Gravimetric Reagent for Indium(III)

NEPAL SINGH, R. C. AGARWAL and B. D. KANSAL

Department of Chemistry, Hindu College, Moradabad

*Manuscript received 25 September 1978,
revised 10 October 1979, accepted 4 March 1980*

INDIUM(III) has been precipitated quantitatively in pH range 4.4-6.7 as morpholine-4-carbodithioate complex of composition $[(C_5H_8ONS_2)_3In]$ which can be weighed after drying at 110-120°. The effect of several diverse ions on precipitation was avoided using suitable masking agents.

Numerous organic reagents employed for the estimation of Indium(III) are described¹⁻⁶. In continuation of our investigations⁶⁻⁹ here we report the application of bidentate morpholine-4-carbodithioate as new gravimetric reagent for Indium(III) and its separation from a number of ions using ammoniacal EDTA as masking agent.

Experimental

The potassium salt of the reagent morpholine-4-carbodithioate has been prepared by treating morpholine in dry ether at 0° with carbon-disulphide and adding potassium hydroxide during four hours under vigorous stirring (Molar ratio; Morpholine : Carbon disulphide and Potassium hydroxide is 1:1:1). The crude product was recrystallised from iso-propyl alcohol. The solution of indium trichloride was prepared by usual method.

Procedure for the determination of In(III) :

An aliquot of the Indium(III) solution (0.02M) was diluted to about 150 ml with distilled water. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.0 by adding appropriate quantity of acetate buffer. The 1% reagent (MCDT) solution (w/v) in distilled water was then added with constant stirring. A white precipitate gradually separates out which was digested on water-bath (60-65°) for about 20 minutes. The precipitate was filtered through sintered crucible (G-4), washed with distilled water and dried at 110-120°.

Effect of foreign ions on the determination of In(III) :

To study the influence of foreign ions on gravimetric determination of In(III), a definite amount of various anions and cations (2-4 fold) were added to a definite quantity of In(III) solution prior to the addition of reagent (MCDT). The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5 - 5.5 using acetate buffer and estimations were carried out as described earlier. It was found that the ions Ba(II), Ca(II), Sr(II), Mg(II), Be(II), Al(III), Th(IV), Zr(IV), NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , citrate, tartrate do not interfere in quantitative determination of Indium(III). The ions $C_2O_4^{2-}$, PO_4^{3-} and BO_3^{3-} interfere. A mixture of ammoniacal EDTA and tartrate masked Tl(I), Co(II), Fe(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Sn(II), Fe(III), In(III) and Ga(III), therefore could not be determined in presence of each other. The ions Ag(I), Hg(II), Pb(II), Cu(II), Pd(II) and Bi(III) precipitate at the same pH range, therefore create interference in their determination. To overcome this difficulty an ammoniacal mixture of EDTA and tartrate is used as masking agent for In(III) before the precipitation of aforesaid ions. The Indium(III) can be demasked by repeated treatment with HNO_3 (dilution and evaporation) and determine Indium(III) using morpholine-4-carbodithioate after neutralizing the adhering nitric acid.

The Indium(III) complex is thermally stable upto 180°. The precipitate settles within few minutes and requires less time for digestion. The digestion above 80° yield low results. It is due to the fact that In(III) dithiocarbamate in contact with water get slightly dissolved. The negative results in estimation of indium might be due to slight solubility of the In(III) chelate. The percentage of negative error varies from -0.26 to -0.29 when the complex was heated at 50-70° (digestion

time 20–30 minutes). The negative error exceeds to -0.38% when the duration of digestion is an hour at 80°.

The positive error for indium was observed in binary mixture of Hg(II) and In(III) only. Mercury(II) was estimated by masking In(III) with ammoniacal EDTA. The positive error might be due to slight solubility of Hg(II) dithiocarbamate in ammoniacal EDTA which is coprecipitated later on. The results of Hg(II) are better than -0.5%. The error of indium(III) dithiocarbamate varies in between +0.18 to +0.24%. The determination of indium in binary mixture (Ag, Hg, Pb, Cu and Bi) required acid treatment which makes the estimation slightly lengthier, inspite of this, the determination of indium is fast and accurate.

References

1. E. N. VINOGRADOVA and N. N. CHUDINOVA, *Zarodskaya*, 1956, 22, 1280.
2. P. SAKELLARIDIS and E. PAPANICOLAOU, *Chim. Chromika (Athens Greeca)*, 1961, 26, 163.
3. A. M. GOLUB and V. M. SAMOILENKO, *Urk. Khim. Zh.*, 1963, 29(5), 472.
4. E. P. FRANCA and R. W. DODSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2651.
5. P. SENISS *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4146.
6. N. SINGH, R. KUMAR and B. D. KANSAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 240.
7. N. SINGH, R. KUMAR and R. C. AGARWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 961.
8. N. SINGH, R. C. AGARWAL and V. K. MAHESHWARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 961.
9. G. ST. NICOLOV, N. JORDONOV and HAVENGOV, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, 33, 1056.

Solvent Extraction Studies of Vanadium(V) in presence of N-*p*-methoxybenzoyl-N-*p*-methyl-phenylhydroxylamine and Thiocyanate

SASWATI P. BAG and SUKAMAL SAHA

Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University,
Calcutta-700 032, India

Manuscript received 7 November 1978,
revised 6 September 1979, accepted 18 March 1980

THE recent interest in mixed-ligand complexes has stimulated the development of new methods of separation and analysis of metals¹⁻⁴.

Binary complexes of vanadium(V)-arylhydroxylamine systems^{5,6} produce blue/reddish-violet 1:2 complexes having the absorption maxima between 510-550 nm. A few mixed-ligand vanadium(V)-oxinate complexes^{7,8} have also been reported.

An account of the spectrophotometric studies on the formation of a ternary complex of vanadium(V) with N-*p*-methoxybenzoyl-N-*p*-methyl-phenylhydroxylamine (I)⁹ and thiocyanate is presented in this paper. The reagent (I) is found to form extractable blue-violet binary complex (λ_{max} at 540 nm at high acidity) with the metal. The extraction of the dark blue-violet vanadium(V) mixed-ligand complex in presence of thiocyanate takes place in the pH range (0.8-2.2) as well as in the acid range of 2-4*N* HCl and is stable over 4 hours at room temperature. The complex absorbs maximum at 570 nm. A hyperchromic effect followed by bathochromic shift in the absorption maxima occurred for the formation of mixed-ligand complex. Different extraction constants ($\log K_{ex}$, $\log K_d$ and $\log K_{mix}$) have been evaluated.

Experimental

Reagents, Solutions and Apparatus :

The reagent (I) (m.p. 128-30°) was prepared following the method described in monograph⁹. Solutions of the reagent(I) was prepared in A.R. chloroform.

An aqueous solution of vanadium(V) was prepared from A.R. ammonium meta-vanadate and the solution was standardised volumetrically¹⁰.

All the reagents, chemicals, solvents etc. used in the spectrophotometric measurements were of A.R. grade or spectro-grade quality.

A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with 1.0 cm glass cells was used for the absorbance measurements. All pH-measurements were made with Elico (model LI-10) pH meter.

Extraction Procedure of Vanadium(V) :

An aliquot of the metal solution (1 ml of 0.1 mg/ml solution) was transferred into 100 ml of separatory funnel, followed by dilute acid (6*N* HCl) and water to achieve pH 1.8 and the aqueous phase of 15 ml. 5 ml of 0.5% (w/v) reagent(I) solution and 10 ml chloroform were added and shaken for 10 minutes. To this solution, 5 ml of 2% standard ammonium thiocyanate solution was added and the mixture was thoroughly shaken for another 5 minutes. The resultant dark blue-violet complex in the chloroform layer was drained out and the aqueous layer was washed twice with 5 ml portion of the solvent, the extracts, combined dried and transferred to a 25 ml standard flask. The volume was made up with the solvent and the absorbance was measured at 570 nm against chloroform as blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance Spectra : The absorbance spectra of the mixed complex [V(V)–I–SCN] [V(V)=7.86×10⁻⁵M] extracted in chloroform at pH 1.8 shows maximum absorption at 430 nm and 570 nm. Subsequent measurements were made at 570 nm against solvent as blank where the reagent had no absorption.